

Timing of Efficient and Undiscovered Portscans

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2013 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20130411> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

During a *penetration test* [1] we were confronted with rather unique requirements:

The requests should be performed as efficiently as possible without triggering an alarm in the system.

Because the target's infrastructure was not maintained by our client (also our target) but by one of their external partners, we were *not* to involve the third party in our security testing. At that point, we didn't know about the ideal timing behaviour of our requests. But this would play a crucial role in our mission in order to perform automated requests during an early phase of the testing. So we found ourselves at crossroads.

Efficiency vs. Camouflage

3. Research

In order to best gauge our possibilities of access we gathered information relating to the detection of many requests (typically during a portscan or a flooding). We defined the threshold using two values:

1. Number of accesses
2. per time unit (in our case, seconds)

To find this data for commonly used products, we used the following sources:

- Documentation (online help, manuals, screenshots)
- Testing (download and installation)
- Source code (if available, i.e. Snort)
- Discussion (forums, rather unreliable)

4. Results

In the following table, the number of requests (Req) per second (Sec). in order to get a unified number that can be compared, we compiled the value nr/1S, the number of requests (nR) per second (1S). The arithmetic average of this number is 85.928.

Product		Req	Sec	nR/1S
Aolynk Broadband Router	▼	5	1	5
Astaro Firewall	▲	100	1	100
Avira Internet Security	▼	50	5	10
Billion BiPAC	▲	100	1	100
Bullguard Internet Security	▼	6	0.6	10
Checkpoint Firewall-1	▼	30	20	1.5
Checkpoint Safe@Office	▼	30	20	1.5
Checkpoint UTM-1	▼	30	20	1.5
Checkpoint VPN-1	▼	30	20	1.5
Checkpoint ZoneAlarm	▼	30	20	1.5
Cisco ASA/PIX	▼	8	120	0.07
cPanel lfd	▼	11	260	0.04
Deerfield VisNetic Firewall	▼	3	10	0.3
Inmon Traffic Sentinel	▼	5	600	0.01
Juniper JunOS	▲	10	0.01	2000
Juniper IDP	▼	20	120	0.17
Juniper ScreenOS	▼	10	5	2
Logsurfer+	▼	100	300	0.33
McAfee Sidewinder	▼	5	30	0.17
Microsoft ISA	▼	10	60	0.17
Microsoft TMG	▼	10	60	0.17
Outpost Firewall	▼	8	1	8

Port Scan Attack Detector	▼	5	5	1
scanlogd	▼	7	3	2.33
Snort	▼	5	60	0.08
SonicWALL	▲	300	1	300
Sophos Endpoint Protection	▼	3	0.3	10
Sophos UTM	▼	3	0.3	10
Watchguard Edge	▼	10	1	10
Zyxel Zywall	▼	30	60	0.5

Some factors stood out. All of them didn't make our work easier:

- Many a product offers *port scan detection*, but only permit to activate or deactivate this feature. There are no *details* or options for granulated settings (requests/second).
- Some vendors that are known for buying other companies and products offer very *inconsistent basic settings* across their products. Examples include Juniper. Contrary to that behaviour is Checkpoint with a rather unified set of values (30 requests / 20 seconds).
- Vendors tend to use *different units of time* for testing. Short backlogs deliver high performance and long backlogs deliver a high rate of detection of long scans. Ranging from 0.3 seconds in Sophos to 10 minutes in Inmon Traffic Sentinel, we found a plethora of values. Products with extremely long units of time ranging in the area of hours have been excluded on purpose.

Figure: Timing of products when detecting portscans

5. Summary

A reliable guideline for the threshold of *port scan detection* is the standard value of Checkpoint products. Thirty requests over twenty seconds is a maximum average of 1.5 packets per second, which is the median of the values in this article.

If you are confronted with the same paradoxical requirements as we were then you should go for *approximately 1.3 packets per second* in order to remain undetected. The offset of 0.2 was chosen as a buffer in order to be absolutely safe and undetected. Using nmap we enabled the switch `—max-rate 1.3` [2] in order to maintain that rate.

However, this view is only capable of dealing with standard settings of any product. The further recommendations by vendors, clients and experts as well as the settings that end up being used have to be looked at on an individual basis.

6. External Links

- [1] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?dienstleistungen.penetrationtest>
 [2] <http://nmap.org/book/man-performance.html>